

Overview of Basic Sanitation in Maccini Baji Hamlet Takalar District in 2022

Yusma Indah Jayadi^{ID}, Yudi Adnan^{ID}, Tiara Hasdin^{ID}, Siti Izzah Fauziah^{ID},
Annisa Nuryasmin^{ID}

Public Health Study Program, Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, Alauddin State Islamic University
Makassar, Indonesia

* Corresponding author: yusmaidahji@gmail.com

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Abstract

Sanitation of a clean and healthy environment is very important in the prevention of various diseases and can improve the health status of the community. This research is observational using a descriptive approach that describes the condition of environmental sanitation. Data was collected by using interview techniques and also direct observation using a questionnaire. The study population was all heads of families (KK) living in the hamlet of Maccini Baji, Ujung Baji Village, Sanrobone District, Takalar Regency totaling 135 families. Respondents in this study amounted to 135 houses stairs. Of the 135 households, 68.9% used tap water (PDAM) as a source of drinking water, 10.4% did not have a latrine, 81.5% households using public toilets if latrines are not available, 85.2% do not have SPAL, 54.1% dispose of waste water around the house, 31.1% no trash can, 71.1% have the type of open trash can, 44.4% of waste handling methods are disposed of into rivers or seas or ditches, 20.7% do not have a septic tank, 96.3% frequency of cleaning livestock cages per month is 0-15 times, and 50.4% has ventilation with an area of <10% floor area. Directions and motivations from the local government regarding the availability of latrines, waste water sewers (SPAL), trash cans, septic tanks as well as counseling or socialization about waste handling and waste water disposal can be carried out at every village activity in collaboration with village cadres and Mutual cooperation activities can also be carried out regularly every month.

Keywords: Basic Sanitation, Maccini Baji Hamlet, SPAL, Latrine

Background

Sanitation according to *The World Health Organization* (WHO) is something supervising business several environmental factors influential physical to man especially to things that affect effect, damage development physical, health and survival life human (www.who.int).

A lot problem must - have environment faced and very disturbing to achievement health environment. So big influence environment so that for improve health status need conducted effort health environment which is effort prevention to related diseases with environment live. Environmental health could cause positive to condition elements living and non-living in ecosystem. When environment no healthy so get sick elements, but on the contrary if environment healthy so healthy too the elements (Riskesdas, 2021).

Impact sanitation bad cause various loss. Loss financial estimated reached 63 trillion rupiah or (2% of GNP), a large amount that should be could utilized for activity empowerment poor people. At level micro, loss other is waste time, increase Health costs, and decrease productivity at level house stairs. In fact, sanitation bad tend trigger conflict social. Sanitation bad result in damage environment. Damage environment take effect to drop quality life whole residents in Indonesia, good poor and rich groups (Riskesdas, 2021).

Based on Riskesdas data year 2018 that the place waste water disposal main from bathroom / place direct wash thrown away to the sewer/time/ river amounting to 68.56% located live in urban areas.

Then proportion highest waste water disposal kitchen direct to the sewer/time/ river namely Makassar City by 82.87%. Proportion the place collection / shelter rubbish wet (organic) inside Most houses in South Sulawesi Province use the place rubbish open that is by 78.4%. According to district / city proportion highest the place rubbish open namely in the District Wajo by 88.66% (Riskasdas, 2018).

Based on results from journal Condition Basic Sanitation in Island Communities Lae-Lae Ujung Pandang District, Makassar City from Most of the respondent's manifold sex woman i.e., 50 (66.7%) with group age 32-41 totaled 24 (32.0%), the level of education head most family _ that is 45 (60.0 %) graduated from elementary school and worked as fisherman totaled 53 (70.7%). The most abundant source of water used is well dig not protected namely 44 respondents (58.7%) who use for necessity washing etc. and 36 respondents (48.0%) who used for necessity cook. Clean water quantity enough namely 73 (97.3%), while quality physical water taste amounted to 10 (13.3%) for quality the physical form of water cloudy, colored, tasted and foamy no found. Ownership toilet namely 35 (46.7%) , respondents who defecate in the sea as many as 40 (53.3%). Ownership the place rubbish amounted to 33 (44.0%), type the place the most trash namely semi-permanent (barrel/ basket) amounted to 28 (84.8%). SPAL ownership is 39 (52.0 %), the most SPAL distance not enough of 10 meters that is 38 (97.4%) (Lae-lae, 2013).

Diarrhea permanent Becomes murderer main but mostly could prevented. More water, sanitation and hygiene good could prevent deaths of 297,000 children under 5 years every year defecate haphazard perpetuate circle Devil disease and poverty. Countries where defection the widest open have amount Dead children under 5 years highest as well as level deficiency nutrition and poverty highest , and disparity great wealth. By general concluded that enhancement the degree of public health that has been achieved until 2020 is description from results Health development in line with repair condition general, situation social and economic Public Regency Takalar (Central Bureau of Statistics, 2017).

By geographical Ujung Baji Village consist from seas and plains low. Same thing with other areas in South Sulawesi, Ujung Baji Village experience change season twice in one year. state topography in Dusun Maccini Wedge have topography lowlands . And by geographic, Hamlet Maccini Wedge is located at the point coordinates 5 ° 27'1,570" latitude south and 119 ° 23'3,213" longitude east be at a height on surface sea. Ujung Baji Village consist Six Hamlets , namely Dusun Maccini Sombala , Ujung Lau hamlet, Ujung Baji hamlet , Galumbayya hamlet, Makkio hamlet Baji, and the Hamlet of Maccini wedge. The boundaries of the Ujung Baji Village that is adjacent north border with Village Sanrobone, next door east border with Village Afternoon , next door south border with Village Maccini Baji, bordered to the west with Village Laguruda. As for the boundaries of the Maccini Hamlet, Wedge i.e.: next to north border with river, next door east border with river, next door south border with the sea, bordering the west with Makkio Hamlet wedge. Based on government data village amount population Ujung Baji Village totaling 1,598 souls, which are scattered in 6 hamlet areas. Based on secondary data year 2021 number population for Maccini Hamlet Wedge totaled 438 people with 37 men and 401 women. Composition amount Head Family (KK) Dusun Maccini The wedge in 2021 is 212 KK. Because of that, researcher analyze basic community sanitation in Maccini hamlet Baji, Ujung Baji Village, District Sanrobone, District Takalar.

Research Methods

Type study this is study observational. study this carried out in the village of Ujung Baji, Hamlet Maccini Baji, District Sanrobone, District Takalar, South Sulawesi. Method data collection through Interview in-depth, FGD (Focus Group Discussion) and observation. Population study this is whole head family living in the village Maccini wedge. Informant in study this amount 135 RT. Visible Variables in study this is scatter drinking water source, distribution latrine which includes type

latrine and if no there is latrines, distribution of SPAL and waste water disposal, distribution the place rubbish containing type the place trash, as well method handling trash. Distribution of septic tanks, distribution livestock which includes distance cage livestock and distribution large ventilation home. Study this done on the month July 2022. Data processing is carried out by descriptive.

Results

Respondent Characteristics

Table 1. Characteristics

Based on Gender in Maccini Baji Hamlet, Ujung Baji Village, Kec. Sanrobone, Kab. Takalar, Prov. South Sulawesi 2022

Gender	Maccini Baji hamlet	Percent (%)
Male	181 People	45.1
female	220 people	54.9
Total population	401 People	100%

Source : Secondary data Ujung Baji Village 2021

Based on the gender characteristics table in Maccini Baji Hamlet, out of 135 RTs, there are 181 respondents who are male (45.1%) and there are 220 respondents who are female (54.9%).

Table 2. Characteristic

Based on income in Maccini Baji Hamlet, Ujung Baji Village, Kec. Sanrobone, Kab. Takalar, Prov. South Sulawesi 2022

Total Family Income	Total (n)	Percent
Rp. 0 – Rp. 3,000,000	109	80.4
Rp. 3,100,000 – Rp. 5,000,000	23	17.0
> Rp. 5,000,000	3	2.2
Total	135	100%

Source : Primary Data 2022

Based on the income characteristic table in Maccini Baji Hamlet of 135 RTs, there are 109 RTs (80.4%) whose total family income is around Rp. 0 – Rp. 3,000,000, as many as 23 RT (17%) whose total family income is around Rp. 3,100,000 – Rp. 5,000,000 and 3 RTs whose total family income is >Rp. 5,000,000.

Distribution of Drinking Water Sources

Table 1. Household Distribution

Based on Drinking Water Sources in Maccini Baji Hamlet, Ujung Baji Village, Kec. Sanrobone, Kab. Takalar, Prov. South Sulawesi 2022

Drinking Water Source	Total (n)	Percent (%)
Bottled water	2	1.5
Water refill	38	28.1
Tap water/ PDAM	93	68.9
Drilling wells/ pumps/ ground water	2	1.5
Total	135	100%

Source: Primary Data 2022

Based on the table of characteristics of drinking water sources in Maccini Baji Hamlet of 135 RTs, there are 2 RTs (1.5%) using bottled water as a source of drinking water, 38 RTs (28.1%) using refilled water, 93 RTs (68.9%) which use tap water/ PDAM, and as many as 2 RT (1.5%) use boreholes/ pumps/ ground water.

Table 2. Household Distribution

Based on the latrine ownership in Maccini Baji Hamlet, Ujung Baji Village, Kec. Sanrobone, Kab. Takalar, Prov. South Sulawesi 2022

Latrine Ownership	Total (n)	Percent (%)
Yes	121	89.6
Not	14	10.4
Total	135	100%

Source: Primary Data 2022

Based on the table of characteristics of latrine ownership in Maccini Baji Hamlet of 135 RTs, there are 121 RTs (89.6 %) that have latrines and 14 RTs (10.4%) that do not.

Table 2.1. Household Distribution

Based on the type of latrine in Maccini Baji Hamlet, Ujung Baji Village, Kec. Sanrobone, Kab. Takalar, Prov. South Sulawesi 2022

Type of latrine	Total (n)	Percent (%)
Goose neck	121	89.6
Cemplung	0	0
No latrine	14	10.4
Total	135	100%

Source: Primary Data 2022

Based on the table of characteristics of the types of latrines in Maccini Baji Hamlet of 135 RTs, there are 121 RTs (89.6%) which have goose neck latrines and 14 RTs (10.4%) which do not.

Table 2.2. Household Distribution

Based on the location of the latrine, if not available in Maccini Baji Hamlet, Ujung Baji Village, Kec. Sanrobone, Kab. Takalar, Prov. South Sulawesi 2022

Latrine Location If Not Available	Total (n)	Percent (%)
Restroom	110	81.5
Neighbor's house/family	25	18.5
Total	135	100%

Source: Primary Data 2022

Based on the table of characteristics of the latrine location if it is not available from 135 RTs, as many as 110 RT (81.5%) use public toilets for latrines because they do not have latrines and 25 RT (18.5%) use neighboring WCs or family WCs for latrines.

Table 3. Household Distribution

Based on SPAL Ownership in Maccini Baji Hamlet, Ujung Baji Village, Kec. Sanrobone, Kab. Takalar, Prov. South Sulawesi 2022

SPAL Ownership	Total (n)	Percent
Yes	20	14.8
Not	115	85.2
Total	135	100%

Source: Primary Data 2022

Based on the table of latrine ownership characteristics of 135 RTs, there are 20 RTs (14.8%) that have SPAL and 115 RTs (85.2%) that do not.

Table 3.1. Household Distribution

Based on Wastewater Disposal in Maccini Baji Hamlet, Ujung Baji Village, Kec. Sanrobone, Kab. Takalar, Prov. South Sulawesi 2022

Place to Dispose of Wastewater	Total (n)	Percent (%)
Shelter/infiltration	19	14.1
River/beach	23	17
Thrown around the house	73	54.1
There is SPAL	20	14.8
Total	135	100%

Source: Primary Data 2022

Based on the distribution table of waste water disposal in Maccini Baji Hamlet of 135 RTs, there are 19 RTs (14.1%) that discharge waste water to reservoirs/infiltration, 23 RTs (17.0%) that discharge waste water to rivers/beach, 73 RTs (54.1 %)) who dispose of waste water around the house, and 20 RT (14.8%) who dispose of waste water to SPAL.

Waste Distribution

Table 4. Household Distribution

Based on Trash Can Ownership in Maccini Baji Hamlet, Ujung Baji Village, Kec. Sanrobone, Kab. Takalar, Prov. South Sulawesi 2022

Trash Ownership	Total (n)	Percent (%)
Yes	93	68.9
Not	42	31.1
Total	135	100%

Source: Primary Data 2022

Based on the distribution table for the ownership of trash bins in Maccini Baji Hamlet of 135 RTs, there are 93 RTs (68.9%) that have trash cans and 42 RTs (31.1 %) that don't.

Table 4.1. Household Distribution

Based on the Type of Trash in Maccini Baji Hamlet, Ujung Baji Village, Kec. Sanrobone, Kab. Takalar, Prov. South Sulawesi 2022

Trash Type	Total (n)	Percent (%)
1. Closed Trash		
Yes	3	2.2
Not	132	97.8
2. Waterproof Trash		
Yes	23	17.0
Not	112	83.0
3. Open Trash		
Yes	96	71.1
Not	39	28.9
Total	135	100%

Source: Primary Data 2022

Based on table 4.5, it shows that out of 135 RTs, there are 3 RTs (2.2 %) that have closed trash cans and 132 RTs (97.8%) that don't.

Based on table 4.5 shows that from 135 RTs, there are 23 RTs (17.0%) which have watertight trash cans and 112 RTs (83.0%) which do not.

Table 4.5 shows that out of 135 RTs, there are 96 RTs (71.1 %) that have open trash cans and 39 RTs (28.9 %) that don't.

Table 4.2. Household Distribution

Based on the Waste Handling Method in Maccini Baji Hamlet, Ujung Baji Village, Kec. Sanrobone, Kab. Takalar, Prov. South Sulawesi 2022

Waste Handling Method	Total (n)	Percent (%)
Dispose of itself to the TPS	1	0.7
Buried in the ground	2	1.5
Burned	50	37
Dumped into the river/sea/trench	60	44.4
Thrown anywhere	22	16.3
Total	135	100%

Source: Primary Data 2022

Based on the distribution table of waste handling methods from 135 RTs, there are 1 RT (0.7%) who dispose of their own waste to the TPS, there are 2 RT (1.5%) that pile up waste in the ground, as many as 50 RT (37.0%) burn waste, 60 RT (44.4 %) who throw garbage into rivers/seas/ ditches, and 22 RTs (16.3%) who throw garbage indiscriminately as a way of handling waste.

Septic Tank Distribution

Table 5. Based on Septic Tank Ownership in Maccini Baji Hamlet, Ujung Baji Village, Kec. Sanrobone, Kab. Takalar, Prov. South Sulawesi 2022

Septic Tank Ownership	Total (n)	Percent (%)
Yes	107	79.3
Not	28	20.7
Total	135	100%

Source: Primary Data 2022

Based on the septic tank ownership distribution table of 135 RTs, there are 107 RTs (79.3%) that have septic tanks and 28 RTs (20.7%) that do not.

Table 6. Household Distribution

Based on the frequency of cleaning the cages per month in Maccini Baji Hamlet, Ujung Baji Village, Kec. Sanrobone, Kab. The Year 2022

Frequency of Cattle Cage Cleaning Per Month	Total (n)	Percent(%)
0-15 times	130	96.3
16-30 times	5	3.7
Total	135	100%

Based on the distribution table of the frequency of cleaning livestock cages per month from 135 RTs, there are 130 RTs (96.3%) who clean cattle pens about 0-15 times per month and 5 RTs (3.7%) which clean livestock cages about 16-30 times per month.

Table 7. Household Distribution

Based on the Ownership of Home Ventilation in Maccini Baji Hamlet, Ujung Baji Village, Kec. Sanrobone, Kab. Takalar, Prov. South Sulawesi 2022

Ventilation Ownership	Total (n)	Percent (%)
Yes, area $\geq$ 10% floor area	65	48.1
Yes, the area is $<$ 10% of the floor area	68	50.4
There isn't any	2	1.5
Total	135	100%

Source: Primary Data 2022

Based on the distribution table of ventilation ownership from 135 RTs, there are 65 RTs (48.1%) that have ventilation with an area of $\geq$ 10% of the floor area, 68 RTs (50.4%) that have ventilation with an area of $<$ 10% of the floor area, and 2 RTs that do not. have ventilation.

Discussion

Drinking Water Sources

Based on the results of research and data collection that we conducted in Maccini Baji Hamlet regarding drinking water sources, it showed that of the 135 RTs, as many as 2 RTs (1.5%) used bottled water as a source of drinking water, 38 RTs (28.1%) used refilled water as a source of drinking water. source of drinking water, and 93 RT (68.9%) that use tap water/ PDAM as a source of drinking water.

Out of 135 RTs, 98 RTs (72.6%) treat drinking water by cooking it first and 37 RTs (27.4%) treat drinking water by drinking it directly. 135 RTs, there are 118 RTs (87.4%) using tap water/PDAM, 12 RTs (8.9%) using drilled wells/pumps/ground water, and 5 RTs (3.7%) using protected dug wells as a source of clean water for MCK.

Water is one of the natural resources that has a very important function for human life, as well as to promote general welfare, so that water is the basic capital and the main factor of development. Human needs for water are very complex, including for drinking, cooking, bathing, washing (various kinds of laundry) and so on. The average water need in Indonesia is 60 liters per capita per day, which includes 30 liters for bathing, 15 liters of washing, 5 liters of cooking, then 5 liters for drinking and other 5 liters, this situation is influenced by the existence of season, because during the dry season it is possible that the demand will decrease as the available water supply decreases.

One of the areas experiencing potential disturbances related to reduced water sources is the village of Jawesari, Limbangan District, Kendal Regency. Although the village is located on the slopes of a mountain which naturally has abundant sources of water, it turns out to be experiencing problems. Based on the initial survey and a brief interview with Mr. Said, the village head there on 4-5 October 2009, it was found that several springs used for the needs of the residents by being channeled using pralon pipes to houses had experienced drought. The water reservoir in RW 1 which is used for bathing and washing as well as the MCK, inside the tub looks moss that thrives so it looks dirty and poses a risk to health, especially the skin. The flow of the pralon pipe and the reservoir near the spring have never been cleaned. (Oktavianto, Nurhayati and Suswati, 2016)

Impact straight from the lack of need water among others, namely the occurrence of failure to cultivate crops and harvests that cause disruption of food supplies, poor sanitation and hunger

which has an impact on the emergence of diseases due to lack of food and malnutrition (Envihsa, 2021).

The Government of Indonesia has established Clean Water Standards in the Regulation of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Indonesia Number 32 of 2017 concerning Environmental Health Quality Standards and Water Health Requirements for Sanitary Hygiene, Swimming Pools, Per Aqua Solutions, and Public Baths. Water that is suitable for sanitation needs is water that is odorless, tasteless, not cloudy or has a low level of turbidity. In addition, the water also does not contain E. coli bacteria and contains low levels of chemicals, such as pH, iron, detergent, cyanide, pesticides, lead, zinc, and others. The standard for clean water for drinking is that it should be protected from sources of pollution, animals that carry disease, and breeding places for animals or bacteria. Physically clean water for drinking is odorless, clear in color, tastes fresh, and is not exposed to direct sunlight or has a cool temperature of about 10–25 degrees Celsius, and does not have sediment at the bottom of the water (Kendal, 2012).

Jamban and Location of Jamban

There are 121 RTs (89.6%) that have goose-neck latrines that are used by all household members, but 14 RTs (10.4%) do not have latrines on the grounds that they have a family home where the latrine can be shared. And there are 26 RTs that have toddlers, 19 RTs (14.1%) use latrines, 4 RTs (3.0%) dispose of toddlers' feces by throwing them into toilets, 3 RTs (2.2%) by planting them, 15 RTs (11.1%) disposal of toddler's feces by throwing it in the trash, 5 RT (3.7) disposal of toddler's feces by throwing it anywhere. The latrines are mostly RTs which, if they do not have a toilet, use a public toilet, as many as 110 RT (81.5%) and 25 RT (18.5%) using the latrine of a neighbor's/family's house if they do not have a toilet.

Sanitation is one of the efforts to overcome some of the physical environmental factors needed by the main creatures that have a detrimental impact on physical development, health and health and survival . The term sanitation also refers to the maintenance of hygienic conditions through the provision of facilities and services for the disposal of human waste such as urine and faeces. Sanitation is related to environmental health which affects the degree of public health. Poor sanitation conditions will have a negative impact on many aspects of life, starting from the decline in the quality of the community's living environment, the contamination of drinking water sources for the community, the increasing number of diarrhea cases and the emergence of several diseases . Ownership of latrines is included in basic sanitation, so everyone should already have a latrine, if the ownership of latrines in the community is low, the higher the number of people who defecate indiscriminately (BABS), where this can interfere with health and can cause environmental pollution (Mukhlisin and Solihudin, 2020).

Based on the concept and definition of the MDGs, households have access to proper sanitation if the sanitation facilities used meet health requirements, among others, are equipped with a goose-neck toilet or plengsengan with a lid and have a septic tank or wastewater treatment system. SPAL), and is a defecation facility that is used alone or together (Mila sari and Annisa Inayah, 2020).

The behavior of open defecation (BAB) still occurs in Indonesia. In some areas, people still open defecation in rivers or rivers. The impact of the disease that most often occurs due to open defecation into the river is *Escherichia coli*. It is a disease that makes people get diarrhea. After that, you can become dehydrated, then because the body's condition goes down , other diseases enter North Sumatra, 2017).

Spal and Waste Water Disposal

Based on the results of the analysis and data collection that we conducted in Dusun Maccini Baji regarding SPAL (sewerage sewerage) it shows ownership of SPAL (Wastewater Sewerage), residents Maccini Baji Hamlet which has SPAL as many as 20 RT (14.8%) while those who do not have SPAL as many as 115 RT (85.2%). and based on the results of analysis and data collection conducted in Maccini Baji Hamlet regarding waste water disposal, it shows that out of 135 RTs, there are 19 RTs (14.1%) that dispose of waste water to the reservoir/infiltration, 23 RTs (17.0%) which discharge their wastewater to river/beach, 73 RT (54.1 %) who discharge waste water around the house, and 20 RT (14.8%) which discharge waste water to SPAL.

Waste Water Disposal Channel (SPAL) is equipment for waste water management which can consist of excavated soil or pipes made of cement or paralon or so on which is used for water disposal in the form of washing water, bath water, dirty/used water, and others. Waste Water Disposal Channel (SPAL) is a channel used to dispose and collect wastewater from bathrooms where washing, kitchens (not from latrines) for rural areas, so that waste water can seep into the ground and does not cause the spread of disease and does not cause disease dirty residential area. One of the sanitation problems is SPAL which is influenced by various factors including education, knowledge, economy, community participation, the role of health workers, community behavior and habits. (Meliyanti, 2018).

Waste is something that should get great attention for the government and society. Waste management is minimal in the community. Household waste in the community is one of the biggest polluters. Waste that contaminate water can come from human waste, factory waste disposal, or waste water from laundry residue. Water that has been contaminated with this waste can cause various diseases, such as: diarrhea, which can trigger dehydration and even death, methemoglobinemia disease or baby blue when consuming drinking water contaminated with nitrates or high in nitrate content, infectious diseases, such as hepatitis, cholera, and typhus, g disorders, kidney, impaired liver function, cancer , birth defects when contaminated drinking water is consumed by pregnant women (Meliyanti, 2018).

By decree of the Minister of Health (Kepmenkes) number: 852/ Menkes/ SK/ IX/2008 which was later strengthened to become Minister of Health Regulation (Permenkes) Number 3 of 2014, Total Sanitation Community Based (STBM) confirmed as a national development strategy sanitation in Indonesia. STBM is an approach to change hygiene and sanitation behavior through community empowerment with the method triggering. To be able to achieve the goal The strategy for implementing STBM focus on creating an environment that conducive (enabled environment), increasing sanitation needs (demand creation) as well as increasing supply access to sanitation (supply improvement). In general, household waste in Indonesia disposes of its waste directly to got (46.7 percent) and without shelter (17.2 percent). Only 15.5 percent who use shelter enclosed in the yard equipped SPAL (sewerage for waste water), 13.2 percent use shelter open in the yard, and 7.4 percent shelter outside the yard. Access service wastewater treatment, in 2014 by 62 percent. According to the place stay percentage the house that has channel waste water disposal more high in urban by 77.15 percent , compared to with percentage house stairs that have channel waste water disposal in the area rural by 44.74 percent (Meliyanti, 2018).

Waste Distribution

Based on the results and data collection that we conducted in Maccini Baji Hamlet regarding waste, it shows that out of 135 RTs, there are 93 RTs (68.9%) that have trash cans and 42 RTs (31.1 %) that do not. From 135 RTs, there are 3 RTs (2.2 %) which have closed trash cans and 132 RTs (97.8%) which do not.

Of the 135 RTs, there are 23 RTs (17.0%) which have watertight trash cans and 112 RTs (83.0%) which do not.

135 RTs, there are 96 RTs (71.1 %) that have open trash bins and 39 RTs (28.9 %) that don't. 135 RTs, there are 135 RTs (100%) that do not have segregated waste bins. Of the 135 RTs, only 1 RT (0.7%) disposed of their own waste to the TPS, 2 RT (1.5%) piled their waste in the ground, 50 RT (37.0%) burned waste, 60 RT (44.4%). who throw garbage into rivers/ seas/ ditches, and 22 RT (16.3%) who throw garbage carelessly as a way of handling waste.

Garbage is an object or material that is no longer used by humans so that it is thrown away. The societal stigma regarding waste is that all garbage is disgusting, dirty, etc., so it must be burned or disposed of properly. All community activities always generate waste. This is not only the responsibility of the local government but also of the entire community to process waste so that it does not have a negative impact on the surrounding environment. Most people think that burning waste is part of waste processing. however, such things can cause pollution to the environment and interfere with health. Attitudes like this are likely to be influenced by knowledge and age maturity . The same example is the Ujung Baji Village, Maccini baji hamlet, one of the villages called Desa Sanah, one of the villages in Sreseh District, Sampang Regency which is still a disadvantaged village due to limited access to transportation which is still in the development process. This problem certainly affects the activities in the village of Sansah itself, especially in terms of cleanliness, namely the difficulty of procuring waste management because it is constrained by transportation equipment and garbage trucks that cannot enter the village. In addition to transportation, public awareness also affects the condition of environmental cleanliness in the village. Both of these things greatly affect the behavior of littering and burning garbage (Elamin *et al.* , 2018).

According to Ministry of Health waste is one of the problems faced by cities in Indonesia all countries, including Indonesia. Even reported by Jambeck et al (2015) that Indonesia is one of the 20 contributing countries plastic waste is spread all over the world polluting the oceans. However, according to According to the report of the Ministry of Environment (2008), most of the waste in Indonesia is in the form of 58% organic waste, followed by waste plastic as much as 14% and paper as much as 9%. More reported that most solid waste comes from households (RI No. 43 20 Permenkes 19, 2019).

Ownership of Septic Tank

Based on our results and data collection in Maccini Baji Hamlet regarding Septic Tank Ownership, it shows that out of 135 RTs, there are 107 RTs (79.3%) that have septic tanks and 28 RTs (20.7%) that do not.

Every day the family's residential settlements dispose of dirty water that must be accommodated and processed in a sanitary manner. What is meant by dirty water is waste water originating from toilets, toilets, bidets, and waste water containing human waste originating from other plumbing tools. Currently, most of the existing methods of managing dirty water do not meet health requirements, both in urban and rural areas, still using the on-site wastewater treatment system in the form of a septic tank. This treatment was chosen because centralized wastewater (dirty water) treatment is still not widely available in Indonesia. In addition, local systems also do not require large costs when compared to centralized systems. A septic tank is one of the equipment in a building where its function is as a sewage treatment plant (waste water), especially from the latrine or toilet. Therefore, the design of a building must be equipped with a wastewater treatment plant, if this dirty water installation is not considered, the consequences will be pollution for the environment, dirty and disgusting for the surrounding houses (Sudarmadji and Hamdi, 2013).

Septic tanks are considered the best way to treat wastewater, but in fact there is still contamination of soil and water through seepage. Distance requirements in rural areas are easier to meet due to lower occupancy densities. Septic tanks are actually not suitable for use in densely populated cities. Even for a very simple house with a narrow yard, it is impossible to build a septic tank that meets the requirements in every house. However, if you make one tank septic for some homes is difficult to manage. In old residential areas that already use septic tanks, it is not easy to convert them into a piping system. The cost of sewerage piping, which usually ends with a sewage treatment plant, is indeed very expensive. Excavation of a very large pipe in the middle of a crowded city will cause problems of disruption to the smooth flow of traffic and the comfort of residents. A sewerage piping system with a sewage treatment plant may only be feasible (feasible) to be built in a new residential area. For this kind of area, it is also easier to require residents to connect to the dirty water pipe. Limited costs force us to temporarily settle for a septic tank even though the knowledge of building installations and wastewater treatment technology is far more advanced. Advanced technology is only applied in the scale of companies (industry, hotels and so on), institutions (hospitals) and luxury residential groups (Sudarmadji and Hamdi, 2013).

Cleaning Frequency of Animal Cage Per Month

Based on the results of the analysis and data collection that we conducted in Maccini Baji Hamlet regarding the Frequency of Cleaning Cattle Cages Per month, it shows that out of 135 RTs, there are 130 RTs (96.3%) who clean cattle pens about 0-15 times per month and 5 RTs (3.7%) who clean the cattle pens. clean the cattle barn about 16-30 times per month.

Sanitation is an effort to maintain cleanliness which includes the cage and the environment around our beloved pets. The environment of our beloved animal includes the room or place where he exercises or plays the cleanliness of his animal, the owner or people who come into contact with the animal and also the equipment used. Poor sanitation can actually become a breeding ground for disease, while good sanitation can actually reduce the spread of germs. Good sanitation will improve the health of animals, owners, handlers, workers or the environment (Ni Luh Putu and Ni Made Marwati, 2012).

In consumption animals, good sanitation can also improve the health of the products produced, for example meat, milk and eggs. Therefore, cleanliness of the cage is absolutely necessary to avoid infectious diseases to the animals that occupy it, especially for animals that have just entered, young animals or animals that have just recovered from illness. Pets will need a clean living environment to be able to get optimal health in their environment. long time. To be able to maintain this, cleaning and using disinfectants on a regular basis is very important to prevent excessive moisture. A moist cage will cause microorganisms to rapidly grow so that it can cause various types of diseases. Cleaning the cage is also the main thing that should not be forgotten in keeping your pet. A dirty cage and environment will become a breeding ground for disease germs and disturb the comfort of pets and become a breeding ground for various kinds of pathogenic microorganisms such as bacteria, viruses, parasites or fungi. The environment in which individuals grow also greatly affects the body's ability to develop its body's defense system. An unhygienic environment will result in disruption of the body's physiological functions so that the animal's body's defense ability decreases. An environment that is too cold or humid will cause the balance of the exchange of substances to be disturbed so that the growth will not be able to grow properly. To be able to create a cage which is always kept clean and healthy, the pet's cage should always be cleaned of dirt and mopped using a disinfectant. Accuracy in choosing a disinfectant is one of the factors that determine the success for animal owners to be able to create a hygienic environment (Akhmad, Isyani and Ikhsan, 2021).

Ownership of Home Ventilation

Based on the results of our analysis and data collection in Maccini Baji Hamlet related to Home Ventilation Ownership, it shows that from 135 RTs, there are 65 RTs (48.1%) that have ventilation with an area of $\geq 10\%$ of the floor area, 68 RTs (50.4%) have ventilation with an area of $<10\%$ of the floor area, and 2 RTs that do not have ventilation.

Based on table 3.9 shows that from 135 RTs, there are 92 RTs (68.1%) which have sufficient lighting and 43 RTs (31.9%) which do not have sufficient lighting.

Adequate air affects the comfort of the room. Ventilation is the process of exchanging clean air from the outside into the room. Good ventilation can ensure smooth air circulation. Air is a very important element for human life. Without air, humans cannot survive because humans need to breathe. Once breathed, humans inhale then exhale air requires 0.5 liters of clean air. Generally humans breathe 20 times every minute, this means that the air needed as much as 10 liters per minute. When humans breathe there is fresh air that enters and there is air that is expelled from the lungs. Lately, many buildings are made only to be inhabited by individuals without paying attention to good occupancy requirements. To achieve thermal comfort conditions in buildings, especially rooms, the use of proper ventilation systems is needed. The existence of a ventilation system in the room will facilitate the movement of air, from outside the room into the room, so that there is a change of air. Lack of ventilation will cause a lack of oxygen in the room which means carbon dioxide levels which are toxic to the occupants increase. Ventilation not only affects comfort, ventilation can also have a negative impact on human health, according to research stating that someone who lives in a house with good ventilation who do not meet the requirements have a risk of developing pulmonary TB by 5 times greater than someone who lives in a house with adequate ventilation. Therefore, the design of a ventilation system or air exchange in one room is strongly influenced by the condition of the ventilator, including the height of the ventilation, the ventilation area, and its position. If the ventilation is regulated properly, both in its placement and dimensions, the air circulation in the room will be good. With good air exchange conditions, the air in the room will also feel comfortable both temperature and humidity (Maulianti, As and Junaidi, 2021).

Conclusion

People mostly use tap water/ PDAM as a source of drinking water and boil water before consumption. For people who do not have latrines, they usually defecate in public toilets and the toilets of neighbors/family houses. Most of the people do not have SPAL and waste water dumps are dumped around their houses. The types of garbage bins owned by the community, namely open trash cans and methods of handling waste are mostly carried out by dumping them into rivers/seas/troughs. For people who have livestock cages, the frequency of cleaning the cages per month is usually 0-15 times per month. Community houses in Maccini Baji Hamlet have ventilation with an area of $<10\%$ of the floor area. Thus, basic sanitation in Maccini Baji Hamlet is still in the poor category, for example, there are still people who do not have private latrines, ownership of SPAL, ownership of trash cans and ownership of septic tanks.

Suggestion

The government in Maccini Baji Hamlet is still lacking in providing information or advice to the community regarding sanitation in the environment. So that public awareness in paying attention to environmental sanitation is still very lacking. Therefore, we can contribute to the importance of sanitation to the community in the form of counseling or socialization about waste management and waste water disposal (SPAL) and can carry out mutual cooperation activities regularly every month to increase public awareness of the importance of environmental cleanliness.

Reference

- Akhmad, N., Isyani and Ikhsan, M. (2021) 'Advocacy on the Importance of Maintaining Health and Cleanliness of Poultry Cages and Handling Healthy Animal Feed in Sasake Village, Central Lombok Regency', *Indonesian Educator Journal*, 4(2), pp. 110–115.
- Article, I. (2020) 'Education to the Community on Utilization', 1(2), pp. 116–124.
- Central Bureau of Statistics (2017) 'Central Bureau of Statistics', pp. 335–58. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-2008-1040325>.
- Elamine, MZ *et al.* (2018) 'Analysis of Waste Management in The Village of Disah, District of Sreseh Sampang, Madura', *Journal of Environmental Health*, 10(4), p. 368. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.20473/jkl.v10i4.2018.368-375>.
- Clean Water Crisis – Envihsa FKM UI 2022. (2022). Retrieved August 12, 2022, from Ui.ac.id website: <https://envihsa.fkm.ui.ac.id/2021/09/30/krisis-air-net/>
- Kendal, K. (2012) 'Management of Water Resources in Jawesari Village, Limbangan District, Kendal Regency', *Journal of Public Health*, 8(1), pp. 17–22. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.15294/kemas.v8i1.2254>.
- Lae-lae, P. (2013) 'BASIC SANITATION CONDITIONS ON THE COMMUNITY OF LAE-LAE ISLAND Basic Sanitation Conditions on the Community Lae-Lae Island Ujung Pandang Subdistrict of Makassar City Magfirah Irhamiah, Agus Bintara Birawida, Syamsuar Manyullei Faculty of Environmental Health Section', 38, pp. 1–12.
- items. (2021). Retrieved August 12, 2022, from Who.int website: <https://www.who.int/publications/m/item/progress-on-drinking-water--sanitation-and-hygiene-in-schools--2000-2021-data-update>
- Maulianti, S., As, ZA and Junaidi, J. (2021) 'Air Adequacy Affects Room Comfort', *JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL HEALTH: Journal and Application of Environmental Health Engineering*, 18(1), p. 19. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.31964/jkl.v18i1.272>.
- Meliyanti, F. (2018) 'Factors Relating to Ownership of Household Wastewater Sewerage', *Aisyah Journal: Journal of Health Sciences*, 3(1), pp. 87–94. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.30604/jika.v3i1.87>.
- Mukhlisin, M. and Solihudin, EN (2020) 'Ownership of healthy latrines in the community', *Faletahan Health Journal*, 7(03), pp. 119–123. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.33746/fhj.v7i03.197>.
- Mukti, D., Raharjo, M. and Dewanti, N. (2016) 'Relationship Between Implementation of Community-Based Total Sanitation Program (Stbm) and Diarrhea Incidence in the Work Area of Jatibogor Health Center, Tegal Regency', *Journal of Public Health, Diponegoro University*, 4(3), pp. 767–775.
- Oktavianto, A., Nurhayati, N. and Suswati, E. (2016) 'Evaluation of the Safety of Drinking Water Sources in Mojo Village, Padang District, Lumajang Regency', *Journal of Agrotechnology*, 08(02), pp. 185–191.
- Knowledge, H. *et al.* (2012) 'Cage in Disease Prevention Efforts', *Journal of the Relationship of Knowledge, Attitudes and Actions of Poultry Livestock Workers with Sanitation Conditions of Cages in Efforts to Prevent Avian Influenza*, 4, pp. 50–56.
- RI No. 43 20Permenkes19 (2019) 'DESCRIPTION OF WASTE MANAGEMENT IN DOMPU MARKET, DOMPU REGENCY', *ペインクリニック学会治療指針 2*, (2), pp. 1–13.
- Riskesdas (2018) *Report of South Sulawesi Province Riskesdas 2018*, Agency for Health Research

and *Development* . Available at:
<http://ejournal2.litbang.kemkes.go.id/index.php/lpb/article/view/3658>.

Riskesdas (2021) "Results of Clean Water Sanitation Riskesdas 2010," *The Indonesian Public Health*. Available at: <https://www.indonesian-publichealth.com/hasil-sanitation-air-Clean-riskesdas-2010/>.

Sudarmadji and Hamdi (2013) 'Septic tanks and their infiltration as a sewerage system', *PILAR Jurnal Teknik Sipil*, 9(2), pp. 134–142.

Utami (2018) 'The Impact of Environmental Sanitation on Public Health in the Coastal Area of Kota Agung District', *Abdimas Dewantara Journal*, 53(9), pp. 1689–1699.

World. (2022, March 21). Sanitation. Retrieved August 12, 2022, from Who.int website: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/sanitation>